

Speculation on Single Photon Thermodynamics

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In (1), a model is presented for describing a single photon as an isolated thermodynamic system with an energy E , entropy S , temperature T , pressure P and volume V proportional to wavelength power 3. Relationships are found for these variables as powers of wavelength (with E being proportional to wavelength power -1 and V proportional to wavelength power 3) using Gibbs free energy $= 0 = E - TS + PV$. (1) suggests that $E = CT$ and uses this to fix the power of wavelength for T leaving S independent of wavelength.

In previous notes, we considered deriving $\exp(ipx)$, the free particle as well as photon x portion of the wavefunction, by extremizing entropy $-W \ln(W)$ subject to the constraint $ikx = W$. This leads to a one dimensional entropy along the momentum direction. Integrating gives S proportional to wavelength. We suggest that this is in keeping with power law constraints obtained in (1), but not $E = CT$. We suggest that the relations of (1) may be obtained using the first law of thermodynamics instead of $G = 0$.

Work of (1)

In (1), a photon is treated as an isolated equilibrium system and (1) assigns it an energy E (proportional to wavelength because $E = pc$), an entropy S , temperature T , pressure P and volume V proportional to wavelength power 3 (in 3-dimensions). A main idea of (1) is to set Gibbs free energy to 0, i.e.

$$G = E - TS + PV = 0 \quad ((1))$$

With E proportional to wavelength and V to wavelength power 3, power law relations are given for S, T and P , namely:

$$S = C_1 \text{ wavelength power } b \quad ((2a)) \quad T = C_2 \text{ wavelength power } a \quad ((2b)) \quad P = \text{wavelength power } \alpha \quad ((2c))$$

This suggests that $\alpha = -4$ ((3a)) and $a + b = -1$ ((3b))

In (1) it is suggested that $E = CT$ so T should go as wavelength power -1. This means that entropy S is not dependent on wavelength.

As a first comment, we ask: Why should E be proportional to T when T is not used to moderate energies as in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case: $f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$?

Photon Wavefunction from Extremizing Entropy

In several previous notes, we suggested obtaining $\exp(ipx)$ (one dimension), which represents both a photon and free particle with rest mass, by extremizing entropy (using W =wavefunction as the probability) subject to the constraint ipx . Thus, one extremizes:

$$- W \ln W + ipx W \rightarrow W = \exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

This is a one dimensional calculation and leads to a one dimensional entropy, it seems:

$$\text{Entropy} = - \int dx \exp(ipx) ipx$$

$$\rightarrow \text{entropy goes as: wavelength because } p = \hbar/\text{wavelength} \quad ((5))$$

This is clearly not the result of (1), but it does not violate the constraint equations ((3a)) and ((3b)) given in (1). In particular, if $b=1$, then $a = -2$ or T goes as wavelength power -2 . One, however, does not obtain: E proportional to T .

The case of PV is independent and follows from V going as wavelength power 3 in the model of (1).

Use of the First Law of Thermodynamics

We find that the results of ((1)) follow from the first law of thermodynamics just as well as from Gibbs free energy being 0, i.e. ((1)). In particular, using E going as wavelength power -1 and V as wavelength power 3:

$$dE = TdS - PdV \quad ((5)) \rightarrow P \text{ goes as wavelength power } -4, dE \text{ goes as wavelength } -2 \text{ and}$$

$$a + b - 1 = -2 \quad \text{or } a+b=-1.$$

Our result ((5)) gives S goes as wavelength power 1, so $dS = d \text{ wavelength}$ and T goes as wavelength power -2 .

Conclusion

In conclusion, a model for a single photon as an isolated thermodynamic system is presented in (1). It is assumed that the photon has an energy E , entropy S , temperature T , pressure P and volume V . All are assumed to be power laws of wavelength with E going as wavelength power -1 and V as wavelength power 3 being known a priori. This leads to P going as wavelength -4 , $S=C_1$ wavelength power b and $T=C_2$ wavelength power a such that $a+b=-1$. (1) assumes that $E=C_3 T$ and so chooses $a = -1$ meaning that S is independent of wavelength.

We consider the case of obtaining the quantum wavefunction $\exp(ipx)=W$ by maximizing entropy subject to the constraint $ipx W$, i.e. by extremizing $-W \ln W + ipx W$. This yields $\exp(ipx)$ and entropy (integrated in one dimension) is proportional to wavelength. Using the

constraints from (1), we find that T goes a wavelength power -2 and that one does not have $E = C T$.

Furthermore, we suggest that the assumption from (1) that Gibbs free energy $= E - TS + PV = 0$ yields the same results as using the first law of thermodynamics: $dE = TdS - PdV$.

References

1. Kirwan, A.D. Jr. Intrinsic Photon Entropy? The darkside of light 2003 Elsevier
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/222420621_Intrinsic_photon_entropy_The_darkside_of_light